

Studies on the Interaction of Metal Ions and their Hydrrous Oxide Sols with Proteins. Part IV. Interaction of Cobalt, Nickel, Silver, and their Hydrrous Oxide Sols with Casein

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Results on the shifts in pH, obtained by titrating anionic casein with hydrrous oxide sole of cobalt, nickel, and silver, indicate that the protein combines with the metal ions of the sols. Viscosity measurements also lead to the same conclusion. The possibility of the metal ion combining with the imidazole groups of the casein has also been indicated on the basis of pH titrations, carried out between the electrolyte solution and the protein.

The electrometric and viscometric studies on gelatin¹ and transfusion gelatin² having been proved to be of great value in ascertaining the binding of metal ions with proteins, these studies have now been extended to a more complex protein like casein. The reaction of this particular protein with calcium is well known³. Lieben *et al.*⁴, Schmidt *et al.*⁵, and others investigated its reaction with other metal ions, but their results lacked precision in view of the uncharacterised nature of the protein used. In spite of the inherent difficulties, mentioned above, it is, however, possible to limit investigations capable of providing indications of some changes at the reactive sites of the protein. With this aim in view the present investigations have been undertaken and the results obtained on the interaction of cobalt, nickel, and silver (made available from the salts as well as their hydrrous oxides) with casein are incorporated in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

1% Casein solution was prepared by soaking pure casein (E. Merck, 5g.) in all-glass, double distilled water (400 ml) for several hours. A 0.1M-KOH solution was then added dropwise with vigorous shaking (using electric Microid Flask shaker; Griffin and George Ltd.) till a clear solution was obtained. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 11.0 and the volume was finally made to 500 ml. The stock solution of the protein was kept in an ice-box to avoid denaturation.

E. Merck KOH was dissolved in air-free distilled water to prepare a carbonate-free solution according to the method recommended by Kolthoff and Sandell⁶. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 11.0 by diluting the solution with distilled water.

1. Salahuddin and Malik, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 603, 609.
2. Malik and Salahuddin, *J. Electro-anal. Chem.*, 1963, 5, 69, 147.
3. Greenberg, "Advances in Protein Chemistry", 1944, I, 121; Chanutin *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1942, 143, 737.
4. *Biochem. Z.*, 1926, 287, 71; 1928, 297, 369; 1956, 322, 386.
5. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1920, 88, 241; *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1935, 19, 127; Mellander, *Biochem. Z.*, 1949, 300, 240; Hipp *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4822.
6. "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., The Macmillan Co., New York, N. Y., 1952, p. 256.

The hydrous oxide sols of cobalt, nickel, and silver were prepared as described earlier⁷⁻⁹ and the oxide contents determined gravimetrically⁹ (cobalt oxide, 1.203 g./litre; nickel oxide, 3.108 g./litre; silver chloride, 7.862 g./litre). The nature of charge was determined by means of a Burton's type electrophoretic tube. All the three sols were positively charged. The *pH*'s of the oxides of Co, Ni, and Ag were found to be 6.50, 6.50, and 7.50 respectively.

Solutions.—Chemically pure samples of cobalt chloride, nickel chloride, and silver nitrate were dissolved in double distilled water to provide the respective solutions. Since a comparative study of the binding of metal ions from the sol and electrolyte was the purpose of these investigations, the *pH* of the electrolyte was brought, as far as possible, to the same *pH* as that of the corresponding hydrophobic sol by addition of the requisite amount of a 0.1*M*-KOH solution. Accordingly, the *pH* of the cobalt chloride, nickel chloride, and silver nitrate solutions were adjusted to 6.50, 6.50, and 6.80 (silver nitrate solution of *pH* 7.50 could not be prepared). The strengths of these solutions were determined by the usual methods and were found to be 3.56×10^{-3} *M* CoCl₂, 4.345×10^{-3} *M* NiCl₂, and 8.65×10^{-3} AgNO₃.

pH Measurements.—*pH* measurements were carried out by a Beckman *pH*-meter, model H, using glass electrodes in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode. Nitrogen (purified by passing through pyrogallol and chromous chloride solution) was passed to ensure an inert atmosphere as well as to stir the solution. The results were verified with the help of a Tinsley potentiometer, Type 33878, using hydrogen and saturated calomel electrodes.

Measurement of Viscosity.—Modified Scarpa's method¹⁰ was employed in the measurement of the viscosity of the mixtures of the hydrous oxide sol and the protein. Mixtures, just similar to those prepared for the *pH*-metric studies, were used with the only difference that those mixtures were chosen for study in which coagulation did not set in. An Ostwald's type of viscometer (diameter of the capillary 0.5 mm; length, 8 cm) and a thermostatic water bath (Townson and Mercer Corydon), maintained at $25^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$, were used.

Procedure.—Following sets of mixtures were prepared for *pH*-metric and viscometric studies:

(i). Varying volumes, viz., 0, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, 14, 15, and 16 ml of the hydrous oxide sols of cobalt (*pH* 6.50), nickel (*pH* 6.50), and silver (*pH* 7.50) were taken in 50-ml pyrex conical flasks. Two such sets were arranged; to one 4 ml of 1% casein solution (*pH* 11.0) and to the second 4 ml of KOH solution (*pH* 11.00) were added; the total volume was made to 20 ml in each case by addition of the requisite amount of distilled water (the total protein concentration in the resulting mixture being 0.2%). Coagulation was found to set in beyond *pH* 9.5, 9.7, and 10.4 for the sols of cobalt, nickel, and silver respectively.

(ii). Similarly varying volumes, viz., 0, 1, 2, 4, 6 ml etc. of cobalt chloride (*pH* 6.50), nickel chloride (*pH* 6.50), and silver nitrate (*pH* 6.80) were mixed with 4 ml of casein

7. Tower and Cook, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, 26, 722.

8. Lottermoser, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1905, ii, 71, 39.

9. Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc. New York, Vol. I, 1945.

10. *Gazzetta*, 1910, 40, 271; Prasad *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1951, 56, 1384.

(pH 11.0). Addition of KOH (pH 11.0) resulted in the precipitation of the hydroxide. Precipitation of the hydroxide also took place in presence of the protein, but in all cases the pH for the onset of precipitation increased. For example, it was found that with the hydroxides of cobalt, nickel, and silver, the pH for the onset of precipitation changed from 6.8 to 8.5, 6.8 to 7.8, and 7.5 to 9.5, respectively, in the case of the salt solutions.

DISCUSSION

Casein with a number of reactive groups of the amino-acid side chains possesses the potential capacity, depending on pH, to bind ions either from the salt solution or the colloid. Since the protein under investigation does not exhibit any detectable chloride in binding, the only possible mode of binding, which can be visualised, is that of the interaction of cobalt, nickel, and silver ions by the available sites on the protein molecule.

FIG. 1

- A = cobalt oxide sol + casein.
- C = " " " " + KOH.
- B = CoCl_2 + casein.
- D = CoCl_2 + KOH.

FIG. 2

- A = nickel oxide + casein.
- C = " " " " + KOH
- B = NiCl_2 + casein.
- D = " " + KOH.

The pH-titration curves of casein (pH 11.0) in presence of increasing amounts of the hydrous oxide sols of cobalt and nickel, each of pH 6.50, do not superimpose on those for the sols and KOH (Figs. 1 and 2, curves A and C) of identical pH. On the other hand, these lie well above those for the sol and the alkali, showing thereby that the action with the anionic protein is different from that with the alkali; this discrepancy can only be explained in terms of the competition between protein and its free base for combination with the metal ions made available from the hydrophobic colloid solutions. Further, the fact that mixtures containing protein and sol remain suspended and that the protein could not be salted out below pH 10.0 also lead to the same conclusion that chemical forces are primarily involved during the interaction of hydrophobic and hydrophilic sols. It may also be pointed out that the marked shift in pH with 0.2% protein

cannot be ascribed to the buffering capacity of the unchanged protein molecules. Useful information regarding the binding of the metal ion by the imidazole group of the protein is also forthcoming from these curves. Since the net effect of dephosphorisation of casein is very small on its metal-ion binding capacity (the phosphate group of the protein is not expected to play any important role in this case), the flat portion in the titration curve (curve A, Fig. 1), which makes its appearance in the pH range 8-8.5, can only be attributed to the interaction of Co^{2+} ion (from the sol) and the imidazole group of the protein. Further confirmation of this view point is also forthcoming from the comparison of the titration curves for electrolyte-casein with that of electrolyte-KOH (Fig. 1, curves A and D), where, too, a shift in pH towards lower values takes place when the protein is replaced by the alkali. A well-defined flat portion was obtained in the pH range 7.4-8.0 (Fig. 1, curve B), indicating clearly the preferential binding of the metal ions through the imidazole group.

The pH-titration curves for nickel and its hydrous oxide sol are similar to those for cobalt in so far as the position of the flat portion in the curves is concerned. In this case also, the experimental results can be explained only in terms of nickel combining with the imidazole groups of casein.

The equilibrium dialysis studies of Fiess¹¹ on Co^{2+} ion binding to native proteins, combined with the fact that stability constant values for the association of cobalt and nickel with histidine are quite high (values of $\log K$'s are 13.9 and 15.9 for the interaction of cobalt and nickel with histidine), lend further support to our view points.

Whereas the titration of casein, carried out in presence of gradually increasing amounts of silver nitrate (pH 6.80), follows the same pattern (Fig. 3, curve B) as that for

FIG. 3

- A = Silver oxide sol + casein.
 C = Silver oxide sol + KOH.
 B = AgNO_3 + casein.
 D = AgNO_3 + KOH.

the above two metal ions, the curve for silver oxide and the protein (Fig. 3, curve A) shows a different behaviour. Here no flat portion in the pH range 6.5-8.5 exists, indicating non-availability of silver ions from the sol to combine with the imidazole group of the protein. A well-defined curvature existing in the pH range 9.2 to 10.4, however, is indicative of a possible binding of silver ion from the sol by the reactive amino group of the protein, available in this pH range. The metal-amino type of interaction does not seem to be predominant with the silver ions from the electrolyte solution (due to precipitation of hydrous oxide in this pH range) although a well-defined flat portion in the pH range 7.8-8.1 (Fig. 3, curve B) provides a strong evidence in favour of silver-imidazole interaction since in the pH range under consideration only imidazole groups

of the protein provide principal sites for the metal-ion binding.

Viscosity Measurements.—Viscosity measurements of the mixtures containing varying amounts of sols of cobalt, nickel, and silver and the protein, carried out under exactly similar conditions as that for pH-metric investigations, present some interesting features.

FIG. 4. Variation of specific viscosity.
A=silver oxide sol. B = nickel oxide sol.
and C = cobalt oxide sol.

FIG. 5. Effect of pH on specific viscosity of solcasein.
A=Silver oxide sol. B = nickel oxide sol.
C=cobalt oxide sol.

From Fig. 4, it is clear that specific viscosity, $(\eta_s - \eta_m)/\eta_m$, increases abruptly when 7 ml of silver oxide, 8 ml of nickel oxide, and 11 ml of cobalt oxide solutions are added to the solution containing 0.2% protein. Assuming that the inflection point in specific viscosity-concentration curve represents a new state of aggregation in the colloidal system, these results may be interpreted in terms of complex formation between casein and the hydrous oxide sols of cobalt, nickel, and silver. Surprisingly enough, the inflection points occur at pH values (pH 8.4, 8.6, and 9.4 for the sols of Co, Ni and Ag, Fig. 5) where chemical combination of metal ions with the protein is indicated on the basis of pH measurements.

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